

Establishing the Accuracy of Voice Analysis with Traditional Allopathic Diagnosis Tools in Any Stage Diagnosis of Diseases

Pre-Illness Stage Diagnosis Tool

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Abstract:- Voice is the holographic representation of not only your personality traits but also certain biomarkers of ill health. The Human Body is like a finely tuned orchestra and is composed of nothing but energy and vibrations with a resonance value we call frequencies.

When the strings go out of tune: The missing or weak frequencies are created which are nothing but an indicator of an initial phase of a Disease pattern developing at the level of the human mind.

Keywords:- Early Diagnosis, Disease Prevention, Preventive Health, Wellness, Body Frequencies, Mental Health, Physical Health, Blood Health, DNA Health.

I. INTRODUCTION

Everything in this universe is made of Energy. Our Body too is made up of energy beginning at the quantum level. An Atom is the Smallest Constitution of an Individual Body responsible for Building Human Blocks.

Each Atom is Composed of :

NUCLEUS: In the Centre Containing Proton and Neutron: Which is Stationary
The difference in the no of such **Protons plus Neutrons** make up different cells.

Periphery: Having Electrons: That revolves around the Atom randomly and at high speed to create the Energy or Life force we call Life. Each Motion brings about certain frequencies as the Electron Moves and the Value of Each frequency depends upon the Composition of Each atom.

Normally each atom has equal no of protons and electrons.

This may become imbalanced More or less when the Disease starts creeping in. Each atom has a different atomic number based on the no of protons and electrons it carries and there fore each atom vibrates at a different frequency.

This creates frequencies inside the human body which is measured in Hz
Each organ has a specific frequency or a range at which it resonates to perform its functions within the human body

Body frequencies are affected by the states of our mind: A **Conscious mind dominant** individual has high Body vibrations while a **subconscious mind dominant** individual has low body vibrations,. Both these states are not considered good for the Human Body.

Frequencies have been used in the form of sound therapies for long to bring about Healing at Mind Body levels , However its for the first time ever that we will be **using body frequencies to not only diagnose mental health , blood health or the physical health** but also Parameters like **chakra imbalances, element imbalances, Immunity strength calculations, Organ Risk calculations** and may more of about 100 plus Biomarkers of Ill health.

Every cell, Organ or a System in the Human Body is resonating or vibrating at a value which we name as the **Working Frequency** for that particular cell, or an organ and is **Measured in Hertz**.

All the cells and Organs Vibrate to perform their respective functions in the Human Body.

There are four types of Frequencies encountered during **Voice Analysis**:

- 1. Normal frequencies :** These are the base frequencies of an organ we call the working frequency @ which an organ vibrates/Resonates to perform its functions For Example: Heart Vibrates at its working frequency to pump blood into the entire body:
- 2. Weak frequencies:** Mean that the Organ frequency is low & that the organ is vibrating at a low resonance and under performing in the Body and **may be at future risk**
 - **Weak frequencies** indicate a future risk @ all levels of Health : Mental , physical or Blood and therefore an indicator of a Disease in the pre illness stages
- 3. Missing frequencies:** Means that the vibrational frequency value of an Organ is compromised and either it has stopped working or about to stop its Normal Functioning inside the body
 - **Missing Frequencies** indicate the presence of a disease not only at the emotional level but also at the levels of blood and the physical body.
 - For example: Schizophrenia, Neurotransmitter deficiencies or a Thyroid or a Kidney Disease.

- **Missing frequencies** form the basis of Voice Analysis as an Early Diagnosis tool in the pre illness stages and should be regarded as an Emergency, requiring either visiting a Doctor or the Hospital and should be taken as an URGENT sign.
- 4. **Hyperactive frequencies:** Mean that the Working vibrational frequency of a particular organ is **higher than normal** and it may be compensating for the missing frequency of another organ/System connected to it.

In case the Hyperactive frequencies are seen at the emotional level: its an indication of the overactivity of the conscious mind. **At the level of the physical body** it means that an organ is showing hyperactivity and must be balanced by any means convenient

If Thyroid; we can say : it may be **Hyperthyroidism**

Every Human Voice is composed of nothing but certain Frequencies of different values :

- An Expression of Each and Every System in the Body**
- An Expression of Each and Every Organ in the Body**
- An Expression of Elements in the Blood**
- An Expression of Each and Every Emotion** in the Mind
- And many more of such **Parameters** or **Bio Markers**.

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STATISTICAL ANALYSIS: EQUATIONS

For Research purposes, We defined proportion of each person based on the notion that, if his/her symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests is matching with his/her voice analysis (missing and hyper frequencies).

If the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests matched with his/her missing/weak or hyper frequencies or both then **we assigned value 1 for those** and if any symptoms or disease did not match with any altered voice frequency then we assigned **value 0** to it. For overall proportion of each patient. we used the formula.

$$p = \frac{\text{Total no. of symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests defined by the altered voice frequencies}}{\text{Total no. of symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests Sum of all values}} = \frac{\text{Total count of the values}}{\text{Total count of the values}} \quad (1)$$

Our test statistic can be defined as;

$$z = \frac{p-p_0}{\sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}}} \quad (2)$$

Now, our test statistic can be given as follows:

$$z = \frac{p-p_0}{\sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}}} = \frac{0.8571-0}{\sqrt{\frac{0.8571 \cdot 0.1429}{98}}} = \frac{0.8571}{\sqrt{0.00124979173}} = 24.2445 \quad (3)$$

95% Confidence interval for our proportion can obtained as follows:

$$CI = p \pm Z_{(\alpha/2)} * \sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}} \quad (4)$$

II. FIGURES AND TABLES

As per our Research that started way back in 2008, here is a list of organs and the frequencies they represent in the human body

Table 1: FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: B-MAJOR

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Brain	B-MAJ
Cerebral Cortex	B-MAJ
CNS	B-MAJ
Right Eye	B-MAJ

Table 2: FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: A-MAJOR

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Pineal	A-MAJ
Pitutary Gland	A-MAJ
Eyes	A-MAJ
Nose & ears	A-MAJ

Table 3: FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: C-MAJOR AND RELATED

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Auto immune system	C-MAJ
Skeletal System	C-MAJ
Bowels	C-MAJ
Prostate	C-MAJ
Bones	C-MAJ & , G-SHARP
Joints	C-MAJ
Teeth	C-MAJ
Nails	C-MAJ
Spinal Column	C-MAJ
	C-MAJ & F-SHARP

Table 4 : FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: D-MAJOR & RELATED

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Ovaries	D-MAJ
Testicles	D-MAJ
Urinary Bladder	D-MAJ
Small Intestine	D-MAJ
Blood vessels & Circulation	D-MAJ
	D-MAJ & A-SHARP

Table 5 : FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: E-MAJOR AND RELATED

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Pancreas	E-MAJ
Adrenals	C-MAJ, E-MAJ & D-SHARP
Stomach	E-MAJ & F-SHARP
Liver	E-MAJ
Gall Bladder	E-MAJ, A-MAJ, D-SHARP

Table 6: FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: HEART AND CIRCULATORY SYSTEM

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Heart	F-Major, C-SHARP & B-MAJ
Thymus	F-Major
Circulatory system	F-Major
Lungs	F-Major
Arms & Hands	F-Major

Table 7: FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: MISCELLANEOUS FREQUENCIES

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Small intestine	D-MAJ & F-SHARP
Hypothalamus	G-MAJ , F-SHARP
Nervous system	F-SHARP
Ears	F-SHARP
Urinary Bladder	F-SHARP
Prostate	C-MAJ, G-SHARP
Lower back	F-SHARP
Circulation of Endocrines	D-SHARP

Table 8: FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: G-MAJOR

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Thyroid	G-MAJ
Parathyroid	G-MAJ
TONSILS	G-MAJ

Table 9: FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: C-SHARP

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Tongue & Throat	C-SHARP
Neck & Shoulders	C-SHARP

Table 10: FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS: A-SHARP

ORGANS	Represented by Frequencies
Bronchi	A-SHARP
Saliva	A-SHARP
Lymphatic circulation	A-SHARP
Muscles	A-SHARP
Mouth & lips	A-SHARP
Spleen	A-SHARP

A few criteria were set up for diagnosis of different diseases as represented by different organs and their involvement in the form of missing, weak or hyperactive frequencies.

Following Parameters were studied during the Research and their correlations with frequencies they represent were studied to establish an accuracy of Diagnosis

Table 11: PARAMETERS AND FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS

S.NO	PARAMETERS	BODY FREQUENCY ASSOCIATION
1.	Pulse	F-Major
2.	BP	C-MAJOR , F-MAJPR , A-MAJOR D-SHARP
3.	Temperature	D-SHARP
4.	Respiratory Rate	E-MAJOR
5.	PO2	E-MAJOR

Following symptoms were encountered during the Research and their correlations with frequencies they represent were studied to establish an accuracy of Diagnosis.

Table 12: LIST OF COMPLAINTS AND SYMPTOMS ENCOUNTERED WITH FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS

S.NO	Symptoms & Complaints	Weak Frequencies
1.	Chest Pain	F-Major
2.	Palpitation	B-MAJ
3.	Shortness of Breath	E-MAJ
4.	Pressure over chest	B-MAJ, F-MAJ
5.	Tachycardia	F-MAJ, C-SHARP
6.	Weakness of Limbs	A-SHARP
7.	Neck & shoulder Pain	C-SHARP
8.	Cough	C-MAJ, E-MAJ, D-SHARP
9.	Hiccough	C-MAJ
10.	Thoracic Pain	F-MAJ ,E-MAJ
11.	Epigastric Pain	E-MAJ
12.	Abdominal Pain	D-MAJ
13.	Lower Joint Pains	C-MAJ
14.	Allergies/Skin Rash	E-MAJ
15.	Hoarseness	C-MAJ, D-MAJ
16.	Fatigue	D-SHARP, F-SHARP, G-SHARP
17.	Acidity	E-MAJ
18.	Constipation	D-MAJ
19.	Loss of Appetite	C-MAJ, D-MAJ, E-MAJ, G-SHARP
20.	Sweating	D-SHARP
21.	Bloating	D-MAJ
22.	Nausea /Vomiting	D-MAJ
23.	Weakness	f-Sharp , A-SHARP
24.	Increased Frequency of Micturition	D-MAJ

		F-SHARP
25.	Lower Back ache	F-SHARP
26.	Pain in Arms and Hands	C-SHARP, F-MAJ
27.	Pain lower extremities	A-SHARP
28.	Swelling /Burning sensation of Lower Legs	F-SHARP
29.	Diarhhea	D-MAJ
30.	Gastritis	E-MAJ
31.	Giddiness	F-SHARP, C-SHARP, A-MAJ
32.	Dizziness	C-SHARP, D-SHARP
33.	Vertigo	C-SHARP, D-SHARP
34.	Fever	C-MAJ, D-SHARP
35.	Weakness of legs	A-SHARP
36.	Flank and Hip Pain	C-MAJ
37.	Headache	F-SHARP, A-MAJ, B-MAJ
38.	Dryness of Mouth	F-SHARP
39.	Ankle Pain	G-MAJ, C-MAJ
40.	Difficulty in swallowing	G-MAJ
41.	Nervousness	B-MAJ, E-MAJ, D-SHARP
42.	Insomnia	E-MAJ, A-MAJ
43.	Backache	F-MAJ
44.	Abdominal Distension	D-MAJ
45.	Heaviness chest	B-MAJ
46.	Body Pains	D-SHARP

Following Diseases were encountered during the Research and their correlations with frequencies they represent were studied to establish an accuracy of Diagnosis.

Table 13: LIST OF DISEASES ENCOUNTERED WITH FREQUENCY ASSOCIATIONS

S.NO	Diseases	Weak Frequencies	Hyperactive Frequencies
1.	Heart Diseases	C-Sharp, F-Major, B-Major	G-Maj
2.	Diabetes	E-Major	F-MAJOR
3.	Lung Disease	E-Major/F-Major	D-SHARP, B-MAJ, A-SHARP
4.	Hypertension	D-sharp, C-Major, F-Major, A-Major	F-SHARP
5.	Hypotension	F-SHARP	D-sharp C-Major, F-Major, A-Major
6.	Anemia	C-Major	E-MAJ
7.	Liver Diseases	E-Major	G-MAJ
8.	Kidney Diseases	D-MAJ ,G-Major	C-SHARP
9.	Thyroid Diseases	G-Major	C-MAJ
10.	Infertility	D-Major	A-Major
11.	Schizophrenia	A-Major	B-MAJ
12.	Anxiety Neurosis	E-MAJ, D-SHARP, A-MAJ, B-MAJ	
13.	Laryngitis	F-MAJ	D-MAJ
14.	Migraine	A-Major	
15.	Vertigo	F-sharp	

ACCURACY CORRELATION WAS DONE BASED ON :

1. Correlation of Parameters recorded with Voice analysis Graph:

- All Vital Parameters as recoded in First Point of Contact were matched with the frequencies detected as : Missing/Weak or Hyperactive and their associations

2. Correlation of Symptoms/Complaints with Voice analysis Graph:

- All complaints and symptoms were matched with the frequencies detected as : Missing/Weak or Hyperactive and their associations

3. Correlation Lab tests reports with Voice analysis Graph:

- All Lab tests reporting were matched with the frequencies detected as : Missing/Weak or Hyperactive and their associations

4. Correlation of Organ/Organs involved as per Diagnosis-and Voice Grid

- After all lab tests and Diagnosis reports, we compared them using voice analysis grids and matched the Frequencies of Organs that showed disease or weakness

For Accuracy Analysis we created 10 Categories

98 patients ,with /without multiple diseases both Male/Female in the age range 10-84, with or without any Diseases, who attended the OPD of Krishna Heart Care, Jaunpur, UP, India were a part of this Research work

III. RESULTS

A total of 98 patients , both Male/Female in the age range 10-84, with or without any Diseases, who attended the OPD of Krishna Heart Care, Jaunpur, UP, India were a part of this Research work

For the purpose of ease we divided all patients into Different categories

A total of **98 patients** with 135 Diseases and who presented with **45 symptoms** and Complaints, were Studied in this Research Project

Each Category of Patients were tested for accuracy of voice analysis by:

1. Frequency correlation With Complaints/Symptoms
2. Frequency correlation With Lab tests
3. Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/Involvement of Organs

IV. CATEGORIES

CATEGORY: HEART Patients: 35

A total of 35 Patients both Male/Female with 10 Different Heart Diseases were studied for accuracy with Voice Analysis and were correlated with, these 3 Parameters for coming to a conclusion

The frequencies responsible for Heart Involvement were checked in each patients voice analysis Grid and a final conclusion was thereafter drawn.

A total of 3 frequencies are responsible for Heart Involvement and also the symptoms or Complaints the patients present with.

OUT OF THESE 35 CASES WITH HEART DISEASES:

Heart is represented in our body by a total of 3 frequencies

- 2 Major Frequencies
- 1 Minor Frequency

Following was the correlation with Frequencies involved:

12 CASES Presented with 1 frequency missing

11 patients presented with 2 frequencies missing

8 patients presented with 1 frequency missing

Table 14: Heart Patients and Missing Frequencies

1 frequency missing	2 frequencies missing	3 frequencies Missing	None Missing
12	11	8	3

All patients with Heart Diseases upon Voice Analysis has 1-3 frequencies Missing or weak

Table 15: Accuracy Correlation: Heart Patients

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
1.	HEART	35	33 were 100% 1 was 50% 1 was 70%	In 34 Patients 100% In 1 Patient: 50%	In 34 Patients 100% In 1 Patient: 50%
			94.2 % accuracy	97.1 % accuracy	97.1 % accuracy

CATEGORY BLOOD PRESSURE: 14

Blood Pressure is indicated by 4 Frequencies: that could either be missing or weak

IN all these cases the body frequencies representing BLOOD Pressure were involved.

Following was the correlation with Frequencies involved:

Hypertension: 10 cases

IN all these cases the body frequencies representing BLOOD Pressure were involved.

Table 16: Hypertension and Missing Frequencies

1 frequency missing	2 frequencies missing	3 frequencies Missing	None Missing
4	4	2	0

Hypotension: 4 cases

Table 17: Hypotension and Missing Frequencies

1 frequency missing	2 frequencies missing	3 frequencies Missing	None Missing
1	2	1	0

All patients with BLOOD PRESSURE ISSUES upon Voice Analysis had 1-2 frequencies Missing or weak, representing BP

Table 18: Accuracy Correlation: Blood Pressure cases

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs	Overall Accuracy Rate in %
2.	BLOOD PRESSURE	14	13 Patients showed 100% accuracy 1 Patient showed 50% accuracy	All 14 Patients showed 100% accuracy	All 14 Patients showed 100% accuracy	3.
			92.85% accuracy	100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy	

CATEGORY DIABETES: 18 CASES

Diabetes is indicated by 2 Frequencies: that could either be missing or weak or Hyperactive

In all these cases the body frequencies representing Diabetes with Involvement of Pancreas were shown either Missing or Hyperactive

Following was the correlation with Frequencies involved:

DIABETES : 18 cases

IN all these cases the body frequencies representing High Blood Sugar levels/Involvement of Pancreas were involved.

Table 19: Diabetes and Body Frequencies

WEAK E-MAJOR	HYPERACTIVE E-MAJOR	HYPERACTIVE F-MAJOR
13	3	2

Table 20: Accuracy Correlation: Diabetes Mellitus cases

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
3.	DIABETES	18	All 18 showed 100 % accuracy	17 showed 100% accuracy 1 : No correlation	ALL 18 showed 100 % accuracy
			100 % accuracy	94.4 % accuracy	100 % accuracy

CATEGORY THYROID DISEASES

Thyroid Gland is represented by 2 frequencies in the human body

- **G-Major**: Represents Thyroid gland
- **D-SHARP**: represents all Endocrines of which Thyroid is a Part of

In all these cases the body frequencies representing Thyroid diseases with Involvement of Thyroid Gland were shown either Missing or Hyperactive

Following was the correlation with Frequencies involved:

- **4 case** Presented with Hyperactive G-Major and Weak D-sharp
- **1 case presented with** Hyperactive D-sharp and Weak G-Major
- **1 case presented with** both Weak G-Major & weak D-Sharp

Table 21: Accuracy Correlation: Thyroid cases

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
4.	THYROID DISEASES	6	All 6 patients showed 100 % accuracy	All 6 patients showed 100 % accuracy	All 6 patients showed 100 % accuracy
			100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy

CATEGORY LIVER DISEASES

Liver is represented by 1 frequency in the human body

- **E-Major**: Represents Liver

Following was the correlation with Frequencies involved:

10 cases with Liver Diseases also had Missing or Hyperactive frequencies representing Liver

In 2 cases no correlation was seen in terms of Liver Diseases and Body frequencies involvement

Table 21: Accuracy Correlation: Liver and Gall bladder cases

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs	Overall Accuracy Rate in %
5.	LIVER & GALL BLADDER DISEASES	14	12 Patients showed 100% accuracy 2 Patients showed 50% accuracy	13 Patients showed 100% accuracy 1 Patient showed 50% accuracy	11 Patients showed 100% accuracy 3 Patient showed 50% accuracy	
			85.7 % accuracy	92.8 % accuracy	78.5 % accuracy	

CATEGORY ANEMIA : 8 cases

Anemia is represented by 2 Frequencies :

- Weak C-Major
- Hyperactive E-Major

5 case Presented with Weak C-Maj

1 case presented with Hyperactive E-Major

IN 2 CASES no correlation could be established

Table 22: Accuracy Correlation: Anemia

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
6.	ANAEMIA	8	5 Patients showed 100% accuracy 2 Patients showed no correlation 1 Patient showed 50% accuracy	5 Patients showed 100% accuracy 2 Patients showed no correlation 1 Patient showed 50% accuracy	5 Patients showed 100% accuracy 2 Patients showed no correlation 1 Patient showed 50% accuracy
			62.5 % accuracy	62.5 % accuracy	62.5 % accuracy

CATEGORY KIDNEY DISEASES : 3 cases

Kidneys are represented by 2 Major frequencies :

- D-Major
- G-Major

All 3 cases presented with Missing or Weak frequencies representing kidneys

Table 23: Accuracy Correlation: Kidney Diseases

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
7.	KIDNEY DISEASES	3	All 3 Patients showed 100% accuracy	All 3 Patients showed 100% accuracy	All 3 Patients showed 100% accuracy
			100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy

CATEGORY: JOINT PAINS: 15

Joint pain are represented by a 4 frequencies:

In 11 CASES these frequencies were either weak or Missing and giving them Joint Pains

In 4 cases no correlation could be established

Table 24: Accuracy Correlation: Joint Pains

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
8.	JOINT PAINS	15	14 Patients showed 100% accuracy 1 Patient showed 50% accuracy	14 Patients showed 100% accuracy 1 Patient showed 50% accuracy	14 Patients showed 100% accuracy 1 Patient showed 50% accuracy
			93.3 % accuracy	93.3 % accuracy	93.3 % accuracy

CATEGORY: ANXIETY NEUROSIS: 10

Anxiety neurosis is a set of emotions associated with or without any disease.

The octave to look for Anxiety neurosis is different than the octave to look for Organ involvement

However we correlated the symptoms and complaints to reach our accuracy 8 out of 10 cases showed symptoms of anxiety while 2 didnt have any correlation with their symptoms and diagnosis made by the physician.

This category there fore requires a larger study group to come to a final conclusion.

Table 25: Accuracy Correlation: Anxiety Neurosis

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
9.	ANXIETY NEUROSIS	10	8 Patients showed 100% accuracy 2 Patients showed 50% accuracy	7 Patients showed 100% accuracy 3 Patients showed 50% accuracy	7 Patients showed 100% accuracy 3 Patients showed 50% accuracy
			80 % accuracy	70 % accuracy	70 % accuracy

CATEGORY: MISCELLANEOUS: 14

This category included those:

- Regular check up: 6
- Abdomen involved : 2
- Infertility :1
- Vertigo : 2
- Laryngitis : 2
- Migraine : 1

4/6 for regular check up matched their symptoms with missing or weak frequencies

2/2 cases of abdomen involvement showed 100% accuracy

1/1 infertility showed missing frequencies matching their disease

½ vertigo patients showed missing frequencies matching their diseases

½ Laryngitis patients showed missing frequencies matching their diseases

1/1 Migraine patient showed missing frequencies matching their diseases

Table 26: Accuracy Correlation: Abdominal pain/Distension

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
10.	ABDOMEN	2	All 2 Patients showed 100% accuracy	All 2 Patients showed 100% accuracy	All 2 Patients showed 100% accuracy
			100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy

Table 26: Accuracy Correlation: Infertility

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
11.	INFERTILITY	1	100% accuracy	100% accuracy	100% accuracy
			100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy

Table 26: Accuracy Correlation: Laryngitis

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
12.	LARYNGITIS	2	1 Patient showed 100% accuracy 1 patient showed no accuracy	1 Patient showed 100% accuracy 1 patient showed no accuracy	1 Patient showed 100% accuracy 1 patient showed no accuracy
			50 % accuracy	50 % accuracy	50 % accuracy

Table 27: Accuracy Correlation: Migraine

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
13.	MIGRAINE	1	Showed 100% accuracy	Showed 100% accuracy	Showed 100% accuracy
			100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy	100 % accuracy

Table 28: Accuracy Correlation: Vertigo

S.NO	CATEGORY	PATIENTS with Multiple complaints /Multi Organ Involvement	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Complaints	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Lab tests	Accuracy Frequency correlation With Diagnosis/ Involvement of Organs
14.	VERTIGO	2	1 Patient showed 100% accuracy 1 patient showed no accuracy	1 Patient showed 100% accuracy 1 patient showed no accuracy	1 Patient showed 100% accuracy 1 patient showed no accuracy
			50 % accuracy	50 % accuracy	50 % accuracy

V. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

For Research purposes, We defined proportion of each person based on the notion that, if his/her symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests is matching with his/her voice analysis (missing and hyper frequencies).

If the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests matched with his/her missing/weak or hyper frequencies or both then we assigned value 1 for those and if any symptoms or disease did not match with any altered voice frequency then we assigned value 0 to it. For overall proportion of each patient. we used the formula.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p &= \frac{\text{Total no. of symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests defined by the altered voice frequencies}}{\text{Total no. of symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests Sum of all values}} \\
 &= \frac{\text{Total count of the values}}{\text{Total count of the values}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, overall proportion of the sample was obtained by taking average (Arithmetic Mean) of individual proportion.

Here, we tested our research through the following hypothesis at 95% level of significance:

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_0: p_0 &= 0 \text{ (means none of the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests are defined by the altered voice frequencies)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_1: p_0 &> 0 \text{ (means some of the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests are defined by the altered voice frequencies)}
 \end{aligned}$$

To test the above hypothesis, we used z-test statistic since our sample size is large enough (more than 30),

Our test statistic can be defined as;

$$z = \frac{p - p_0}{\sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}}}$$

Where,
 p is our sample proportion
 p₀ is our hypothetical proportion

q= 1-p i.e., proportion of undefined symptoms etc.
n is our sample size

So, from our study we have,

p=0.8571
p₀=0
q=1-0.8571=0.1429
n=98

Now, our test statistic can be given as follows:

$$z = \frac{p - p_0}{\sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}}} = \frac{0.8571 - 0}{\sqrt{\frac{0.8571 * 0.1429}{98}}} = \frac{0.8571}{\sqrt{0.00124979173}} = 24.2445$$

The P-value was given as,

P-value=P(z>24.2445) =0

Since, our p-value is equal to 0, which is less than 0.05. So, there are enough evidence to reject our null hypothesis and we can conclude that some proportion of the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests is defined by the altered voice frequencies.

Similarly, we can test our hypothesis for the proportion of more than 75% is explained by the altered voice frequencies)

Here, we will test our research through the following hypothesis at 95% level of significance:

H₀: p₀
= 0 (means none of the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests are defined by the altered voice frequencies)

H₁: p₀
> 0 (means some of the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests are defined by the altered voice frequencies)

To test the above hypothesis, we used Z-test statistic since our sample size is large enough (more than 30), our test statistic can be defined as;

$$z = \frac{p - p_0}{\sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}}}$$

Where,

p is our sample proportion
p₀ is our hypothetical proportion
q= 1-p i.e., proportion of undefined symptoms etc.
n is our sample size

So, from our study we have,

p=0.8571
p₀=0.75
q=1-0.8571=0.1429
n=98

Our test statistic can be given as follows:

$$z = \frac{p - p_0}{\sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}}} = \frac{0.8571 - 0.75}{\sqrt{\frac{0.8571 * 0.1429}{98}}} = \frac{0.1071}{\sqrt{0.00124979173}} = 3.0295$$

P-value can be given as,

p-value=P(z>3.0295) =0.0012248

Since, our p-value is equal to 0.0012248, which is less than 0.05. So, there are enough evidence to reject our null hypothesis and we can conclude that there are more than 75% of the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests is defined by the altered voice frequencies.

95% Confidence interval for our proportion can obtained as follows:

$$CI = p \pm Z_{(\alpha/2)} * \sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}}$$

$$CI = p \pm Z_{(\alpha/2)} * \sqrt{\frac{pq}{n}} = 0.8571 \pm 1.96 * \sqrt{\frac{0.8571 * 0.1429}{98}} = [0.9263, 0.7878]$$

So, from our obtained result of Confidence Interval, we can say that we are 95% confident that through analysis of altered voice frequencies we can define in between 92.6% to 78.7% of the symptoms, clinical analysis, and lab tests results of any patient.

That is the correlation between the accuracy of the 2 Variables used:

Voice Analysis and Traditional Diagnosis tools

We can say that an accuracy of correlation in 3 different parameters utilized, falls between 78.7% to 92.6% in all the categories of Diseases defined for the Purpose of Research.

Accuracy Correlation :

Also in order to understand the accuracy of Voice Analysis further, we calculated these 2 parameters using different formulas :

1. Sensitivity
2. Specificity

For 3 Different Parameters:

1. Weak frequencies
2. Missing frequencies
3. Hyperactive frequencies

Table 29: Accuracy Correlation: Weak Frequencies

WEAK FREQUENCIES			
		Positive	Negative
SYMPTOMS	Positive	(TP)85	(FP)6
	Negative	(FN)3	(TN)4

Specificity = 40%

Sensitivity = 96%

PPV (Positive Predictive value) = 0.93

NPV (negative Predictive value) = 0.57

The sensitivity is 96% it means there are 96% chances that if the voice analysis is showing the weak frequencies, the patient has the target disease.

The specificity : 40% means that if the patient doesn't have the target disease the voice analysis will show no weak frequencies.

As the PPV is .93 (it means that the probability of having a disease is .93 if the frequencies are low or symptoms are positive)

And NPV is .57 (it means that the probability of not having a disease is .57 if the there are no symptoms or weak frequency)

Table30: Accuracy Correlation: Missing Frequencies

MISSING FREQUENCY			
		Positive	Negative
Symptoms	Positive	47	44
	Negative	2	5

Specificity= 10.2%

Sensitivity= 95%

PPV (Positive Predictive value) = 0.51

NPV (negative Predictive value) = 0.71

The sensitivity is 95% means there are 95% chances that if the voice analysis is showing **missing frequencies**, the patient has the target disease.

The specificity : 10.2 % means that if the patient doesn't have the target disease the voice analysis will show no missing frequencies.

As the PPV is .51 (it means that the probability of having a disease is .51 if the frequencies are missing or symptoms are positive)

And NPV is .71 (it means that the probability of not having a disease is .71 if the there are no symptoms or missing frequencies)

Table31: Accuracy Correlation: Hyperactive Frequencies

HYPERACTIVE FREQUENCY			
		Positive	Negative
Symptoms	Positive	65	26
	Negative	2	5

Specificity = 0.16%

Sensitivity= 0.97%

PPV (Positive Predictive value) = 0.71

NPV (negative Predictive value) = 0.71

The sensitivity is 0.97% it means there are 0.97% chances that if the voice analysis is showing hyperactive frequencies, the patient has the target disease.

The specificity : 0.16% means that if the patient doesn't have the target disease the voice analysis will show no hyperactive frequencies.

As the PPV is .71 (it means that the probability of having a disease is .71 if the frequencies are hyperactive or symptoms are positive)

And NPV is .71 (it means that the probability of not having a disease is .71 if the there are no symptoms or hyperactive frequencies)

Table 32: Accuracy Correlation: Traditional Vs Voice Analysis

Voice analysis			
		Positive	Negative
Traditional analysis	Positive	87	7
	Negative	0	4

In terms of Comparing the 2 variables, we found out a 100% sensitivity and 36% specificity

Meaning that:

Sensitivity of 100 % shows that if the voice analysis is showing **missing frequencies**, the Traditional tools with correlate with symptoms/lab tests and Final Diagnosis

Specificity of 0.36 shows that if the patient doesn't have the target disease the voice analysis will show no missing/weak / hyperactive frequencies.

PPV = 0.92, NPV = 1

VI. CONCLUSION

While the presence of **weak and missing frequencies** is an indicator of Organ risk or Organ involvement with good sensitivity values ranging from **92 to 100%** using different formulas for statistical analysis , the presence and absence of **Hyperactive frequencies bear very little relation ship** to

the presence or Absence of disease in terms of Organ risk or Organ involved.

Both sensitivity and Specificity values as calculated are suggestive of the accuracy that voice analysis has that is at par with the tools used in medicine at this moment.

Using the 3 Parameters for the 2 variables as mentioned also gives us the accuracy of voice analysis between **78-92%** when compared with the traditional tools of diagnosis.

An overall accuracy of value of 85.17% using of all 3 parameters in terms of symptoms explained as the final result ,gives us a good indication of the accuracy of voice analysis when it comes to diagnosis of a disease which is already present at the physical or organ level, at the time of patient presenting to a hospital with multiple complaints and symptoms.

The Health care industry is a fast growing and changing paradigm in the recent times and especially Covid-19 has generated much awareness and infused seeds of newer technologies that are coming up fast to keep pace with the Requirement and need of the hour.

Voice Analysis as a new diagnosis tool that fulfills all guidelines for secondary disease prevention: 1984 GENEVA CONVENTION: W.H.O is not only evolving with respect to its early **diagnosis capabilities** in cases with no symptoms to its **ability to diagnose diseases at par** with the traditional diagnosis tools like X-RAY, ECG, Doppler, ECHO etc

Voice analysis has shown to have excellent diagnosis capabilities and accuracy correlation with greater than 90% in all categories selected for research, with the Traditional Diagnosis tools.

Understanding Body frequencies in details in therefore the key to understand the Human Body Dynamics so that we can utilize this knowledge to learn and implement it further for diagnosing various diseases with less hazardous and less painful and less expensive procedures.

REFERENCES

(Instructions: mention recent articles relevant to the study subject and enumerated according to their order of appearance in the text).

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